

PREPARATION OF BIODEGRADABLE THERMOPLASTIC USING ACETYLATED KRAFT LIGNIN

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1 Introduction

As a global attention to environmentalism has been rapidly increased, demands for a fully environment-friendly product also increased. At this point, many researches are developing better bioplastic materials already, but the raw materials for thermoplastics are not only limited to well-known kinds (starch, PLA, PHA and so on) but also the processing costs are still higher than current commodity polymers, that is, synthetic polymers. In other words, even the demands are highly increased and keep on increasing, the growth of bioplastic technologies and industries is being delayed by the reasons.

Meanwhile, kraft lignin, a by-product of kraft process, is a valuable raw material as a natural resin in the emerging bioplastic market because it is an abundant, cheap and biodegradable resource as well as has a possibility to be modified desirably because it has a nature that has phenyl propane unit structures with various functional groups including aromatic and aliphatic hydroxyl (-OH), methoxyl (-OCH₃), carbonyl (-C=O) groups and the others [1]. The functional groups can be chemically modified by well-known methods such as esterification, etherification and copolymerization. Thus, it is possible to modify the properties of lignin and to predict their properties in some extent. From among the processes, acetylation, which results the substitution of hydroxyl group to acetyl groups (-COCH₃), is highly promising process for thermoplastic technologies. Furthermore, the resulting lignin products may become hydrophobic because of removal of hydrogen bonding sites, thus it may be well blended with other hydrophobic polymers, practically synthetic polymers such as PE, PET, PP, PS and so on [2]. Furthermore, kraft lignin is a biodegradable resource after treating with the highly alkaline Kraft process [3], thus it can be

considered as suitable raw material for thermoplastics.

In this point of view, we have investigated the potential of chemically modified lignin, especially acetylated kraft lignin, as a thermoplastic polymer for bioplastic and biocomposite materials. So the objective of this study is to develop a thermoplastic polymer using acetylated kraft lignin.

2 Experimental methods

2.1 Acetylation of kraft lignin

Pine kraft lignin (INDULIN® AT, MeadWestvaco Co., USA), hereafter SKL, was acetylated to produce a thermoplastic polymer. 200g powder-form SKL was placed in an Erlenmeyer flask followed by the addition of 234mL acetic anhydride (97.0%, Junsei Chemical, Japan). Then the flask was heated at 80°C for about an hour. Next, large amount of boiling deionized water was added to the flask to stop the acetylation and to hydrolyze remaining acetic anhydride to acetic acid. Coagulated solid mass was recovered and washed with boiling water in numerous times until the water becomes neutral. Next, the solid mass was washed with methyl alcohol (99.5%, Samchun Chemical, Korea) to remove remaining salts in SKL. Finally, the acetylated SKL (hereafter ASKL) was vacuum-dried overnight at approximately 60°C. Finally, ASKL was milled with a mortar for further blending with various synthetic polymers.

ASKL was easily dissolved by acetone, but not be dissolved in water and some organic solvents including methyl alcohol and ethyl alcohol. ASKL was thermally plasticized at approximately 150°C.

Photo. 1 represents the appearance of ASKL before and after hot-pressing.

Photo. 1. Thermoplastic ASKL.
(Left: before hot-pressed, Right: after hot-pressed)

2.2 Preparation of ASKL-synthetic polymer blend films

Polymer Blending ASKL powder was blended with various synthetic polymer pellets including LDPE, PET, PP and PS. ASKL and synthetic polymers which dried at approximately 60°C were placed in beakers with different weight ratios (0:100, 25:75, 50:50, 75:25 and 100:0). Then the beakers were placed in an oil bath at 170±0.5°C and then manually blended with a stainless rod. In case of ASKL-PET, the temperature was set to 175±0.5°C because the melting temperature of PET was approximately 169°C.

Film Formation ASKL-synthetic polymer blends were hot-pressed by the two post manual hydraulic press (#2699, Carver Inc., USA) to produce thermoplastic polymer blend films. 30g of each polymer blends were placed between stainless plates and then placed in the press which preheated to 170±1°C (180±1°C, in case of ASKL-PET blends). Then the blends were hot-pressed readily with 100 psi for 5 minutes and cooled to ambient temperature. Next, the thermoplastic polymer blend films were detached from the plates. The average thicknesses of prepared films were approximately 0.6-0.7 mm. **Photo. 2** represents the representative appearance of ASKL-PET blend film (weight ratio = ASKL 25: 75 PET).

Density Measurement To investigate the relationship between our experimental results and Rule of Mixtures, densities of ASKL and synthetic polymers were determined. Weight and volume of each pure polymer films tailored as a rectangular form were determined and then densities were calculated. The densities of each pure polymer are presented on **Table 1**.

Photo. 2. ASKL-PET blend film (30:70 v/v %).

Table 1. Densities of ASKL and synthetic polymers used in this study.

	ASKL	LDPE	PET	PP	PS
Density (g/cc)	1.05	1.10	1.36	0.92	1.04

2.3 Tensile tests

Preparation of Tensile Specimens Prepared thermoplastic polymer blend films were die-cut (ASTM D412, die type C) into dumbbell-shape specimens for further tensile tests with assuming the specimens are isotropic.

Photo. 3 represents the representative appearance of fractured tensile specimens with different ASKL-LDPE blend ratios.

Tensile tests Universal testing machine (LRXPlus, LLOYD Instruments, UK) was used for investigating tensile properties of the polymer blend films. Young's modulus, yield strength, breaking strength, elongation at yield and elongation at break were determined. The test was conducted according to ASTM standards; Gauge length was 25.4 mm and tensile loading speed was 500 mm/min.

In some case the tensile tests could not be conducted due to the severe brittleness of specimens (ASKL 75 wt% vs. LDPE, PP or PS 25 wt%).

Photo. 3. Fractured dumbbell-shaped tensile specimens with different ASKL volume fractions.

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Tensile Properties

Fig. 1-5 present the Young's modulus, yield strength, breaking strength, elongation at yield and elongation at break of ASKL-synthetic polymer blends as a function of ASKL volume fraction, respectively.

Young's modulus of ASKL-synthetic polymer blends has increased with the increase of ASKL volume fraction in the range of 0 to approximately 0.2-0.5, which depend on the type of blended synthetic polymer. In this case it is assumed that shear force derived from two compositions, namely, ASKL and the synthetic polymer results the increase of the initial modulus.

Yield strength and elongation at yield at break of ASKL-synthetic polymer blends show a linear trend in common that the values are decreased with the increase of ASKL volume fraction. However, elongation at break of ASKL-synthetic polymer blends is exponentially decreased with the increase.

Breaking strengths of ASKL-synthetic polymer blends also have decreased with the increase of ASKL volume fraction, but in case of ASKL-PET blends a remarkable increase of the strength has observed at 0.25 v/v% of ASKL. In this case it is assumed that there are some synergistic interactions between those two compositions or the shear force comes from elongation is quite high. Since we have set the initial assumption up as the blends will show linear trends, the unusual result will be considered in detail to our next studies.

Since the lignin inhibit the packing of linear synthetic polymers due to their amorphous monomer structure, it is assumed that an improvement of mechanical strength via blending lignin with synthetic polymers is hard to be realized unless the lignin is bonded with the linear polymer by some kind of bond which stronger than hydrogen bond network between packed linear polymers.

Fig. 1. Young's modulus of ASKL-synthetic polymer blends.

Fig. 2. Yield strengths of ASKL-synthetic polymer blends.

Fig. 3. Breaking strengths of ASKL-synthetic polymer blends.

Fig. 4. Elongation at yield data of ASKL-synthetic polymer blends.

Fig. 5. Elongation at break data of ASKL-synthetic polymer blends.

3.2 Discussion

Hydrolysis during acetylation Partial hydrolysis could be occurred during the acetylation of SKL because the reaction was in highly acidic condition. However, it can be thought that the hydrolysis products have relatively smaller molecular structure so that the products may have a bigger molecular mobility. In any case, pH of the reacting solution can be adjusted by mixing pyridine or toluene [4]. We are currently investigating the effect of pH on the hydrolysis of SKL thus it will be considered in our next studies.

Low strength of pure ASKL films It is obvious that ASKL prepared in this study is highly compatible with various synthetic polymers, but ASKL film

could not be prepared for itself because of following suggestions; first, ASKL has weak intermolecular interactions. Since the hydroxyl groups in lignin are fully substituted to acetyl groups, it is assumed that the pure ASKL shows a severe brittleness.

In this point of view, it is assumed that a secondary derivatization of ASKL should be an alternative method for solving problems involved in the brittle nature of SKL. This will be considered in our next studies.

Processing Temperature Even though ASKL is vacuum-dried overnight, the final ASKL films have a lot of voids inside and surface. In TGA-DSC result, SKL shows a thermal degradation over 100 °C (not in figures). Therefore, it is assumed that some gas products generated by the thermal degradation results the generation of voids in ASKL film.

Although reduced mechanical properties of the blends caused by the voids can be mathematically corrected, it is necessary to remove the cause of voids. A possible method for that is an improving thermal stability of ASKL by purification or a removing low molecular weight compounds. Thus, an investigation on the mechanical properties of purified ASKL and various synthetic polymer blends will be conducted in our next studies.

Compatibility with the other synthetic polymers Because the compatibility of ASKL and PLA was relatively lower than the other synthetic polymers (PE, PET, PP, PS and so on), mechanical properties of ASKL-PLA blends could not be measured. In this case, it is assumed that PLA molecules have assembled themselves via their own carboxyl groups and ether bonds, which results the low compatibility. In regard to that, a solubility parameter of polymer is considered as an indicator of compatibility. Meanwhile, it is expected that the solubility parameter of ASKL can be adjusted by controlling the degree of acetylation, thus the relationship between degree of acetylation and solubility parameter will be handled in our next studies.

Biodegradation products It is known that some phenolic compounds are produced during rapid biodegradation by microorganisms. The detailed information will be provided in our next studies. In addition, because the final products prepared in this study are not fully biodegradable due to the synthetic polymers, thermoplastics made of pure modified SKL will be investigated.

4 Conclusions

Softwood kraft lignin (SKL) was acetylated to produce biodegradable thermoplastics. Since the pure ASKL film was too brittle to be used solely, ASKL and various synthetic polymers were blended and molded as a film-shape. In this procedure, manually blended ASKL-synthetic polymer blends were hot-pressed by a two post manual hydraulic press at 170-175°C depend on each polymer properties. Young's modulus of ASKL-synthetic polymers were increased with the increase of ASKL volume fraction and showed peaks at approximately 0.25-0.5 v/v%. Most of mechanical properties of ASKL-synthetic polymers showed the linear decrease with the increase of ASKL volume fraction, with some exceptions.

The developed ASKL thermoplastic is suitable to be used as polymer blends and further properties will be handled in our next studies.

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